

Efficacy of Wet Cupping (Hijama) Therapy in Alleviating Mechanical Neck Pain: A Clinic-Based Study of Karachi, Pakistan

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Abstract

Background: Neck pain constitutes a significant cause of disability worldwide. Wet cupping (Hijama therapy) is a part of complementary alternative medicine purported to relieve musculoskeletal pain. **Objective:** This study evaluated the clinical efficacy of single Hijama session on pain intensity and disability among patients with mechanical neck pain. **Methods:** Fifty adults with mechanical neck pain were recruited from Hijama clinics in Karachi. Pain severity and functional disability were assessed using the Visual Analog Scale (VAS) and Neck Disability Index (NDI) 48 hours after intervention. A standardized wet cupping session was administered. **Results:** Participants (98% female, aged 19–60 years) showed significant reductions in mean VAS (65%) and NDI (46%) scores post-intervention ($p < 0.005$). **Conclusion:** A single session of Hijama significantly reduced neck pain and disability, indicating its potential as a cost-effective, low-risk adjunct therapy.

Keywords: Neck pain; wet cupping; Hijama; Visual Analog Scale; Neck Disability Index

Introduction

Neck pain, a prevalent musculoskeletal condition, affected an estimated 203 million people worldwide in 2020, with projections indicating an increase to 269 million by 2050 (Wu, et al., 2024). This condition imposes a significant socioeconomic burden through reduced productivity, increased healthcare utilization, and work absenteeism (Kazeminasab, et al., 2022).

Although traditionally associated with older adults, neck pain is now increasingly observed among younger populations, largely due to sedentary lifestyles and prolonged screen exposure (Kazeminasab, et al., 2022). In Pakistan, a notably high prevalence has been reported among students, educators, and healthcare professionals (Mughal, et al., 2024; Ahmed, et al., 2023, Ghafoor, et al., 2024; Ghauri, et al., 2022). For clinical evaluation, standard tools such as the Visual Analog Scale (VAS) and the Neck Disability Index (NDI) are widely accepted for their validity and reliability in assessing pain intensity and functional impairment (Saltychev, et al., 2024; Delgado, et al., 2018).

In recent years, there has been a growing public interest including Pakistan towards complementary and alternative therapies (CAM) for musculoskeletal pain management (Mushtaq, & Nini, 2025; Saeed, et al.,

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2023). Hijama therapy is one the CAM which involves applying localized negative pressure followed by superficial skin incisions to draw out blood (Niazi, Khan, & Jamil, 2023). It is increasingly being studied for its potential analgesic and anti-inflammatory properties in pain management (Kouser, et al., 2021; Khan, et al., 2023; Javeria, Obaid, & Naseem, 2021).

This study aims to assess the therapeutic effectiveness of Hijama therapy in individuals diagnosed with mechanical neck pain

Methodology

This was a cross-sectional experimental study conducted from January to August 2024 at two Hijama clinics of Karachi. A total of 50 adult participants presenting with non-specific mechanical neck pain and voluntarily seeking Hijama therapy were recruited. The sample size estimation was based on paired mean difference analysis with a power of 0.80, significance level of 0.05, and medium effect size (Dhand, & Khatkar, 2014).

Inclusion Criteria

Adults with mechanical neck pain with no recent change in their routine medication in the past four weeks.

Exclusion Criteria

Patients whose neck pain was attributed to traumatic, post-surgical, inflammatory, or neoplastic causes were excluded from the study. Individuals using corticosteroids, opioids, or anticoagulant medications were also not eligible. Additionally, participants with comorbid conditions such as uncontrolled diabetes or diagnosed mental health disorders were excluded.

Intervention Protocol

Patients underwent a standardized Hijama session. Following palpation and massage of trigger points, 4-6 vacuum-induced glass cups were applied. Superficial incisions were made to facilitate bloodletting. Additional cups were applied at acupoint LI-4. The entire session was supervised by a certified Hijama therapist. Adverse effects were monitored, and post-procedure instructions were provided.

Pain Assessment

VAS and NDI scores were recorded 48 hours after the intervention. VAS consists of 10 cm or 100 mm horizontal lines suggesting two extremes i.e. no pain at extremes left to severe pain at extreme right. The patient is asked to mark on the line at the point which they feel best represent their perception of pain (Delgado, et al., 2018). The VAS score is obtained by measuring the millimeters from the left end of line to the point marked by the patient. The following cut points are often suggested i.e. no pain (0–4 mm), mild pain (5–44 mm), moderate pain (45–74 mm), and severe pain (75–100 mm).

NDI consist of 10 questions which measure the patient self-reported disability associated with neck pain. These questions are related to daily activities such as personal care, lifting, reading, work, driving, sleeping, recreational activities, pain intensity, concentration and headache. Each answer is evaluated on a scale ranging from 0 (no disability) to 5 (Howell, 2011). The value against each answer is added and the total is multiplied by 2. Therefore, the patient disability was assessed from an overall score out of 100. The minimal clinical important change was reported to be 5-10%. The higher the NDI score means, the larger the disability perception by patients due to neck pain (Saltychev, et al., 2024).

Statistical Analysis

Data was analyzed using SPSS 20.0. Paired t-tests assessed differences in mean scores. A p-value < 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Results

The patient demography showed predominantly female patients (98%). The age groups include approximately equal percentages of adult (49%) and middle age (47%) patients.

In this study 39% were housewife ,15 % were working and 2 % were students. Among them 89% were married, 24% were educated till primary level,19% have secondary level ,17% intermediate ,28% graduate and 8 % had the literacy of post-graduation.

Duration of pain was less than 6 weeks in 21% of patients and it was more than 6 weeks in 78%. The pain was associated with strenuous activity or exercise or heavy lifting in 30 %. It was associated with 20% due to sedentary lifestyle or during computer or cellphone use or reading. Bad sleep posture and use of poor pillow was associated in 11%. Psychological stresses were found in 26% of neck sufferers.The type of medication used before hijama therapy is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Alternative Treatment Usage Before Undergoing Hijama Therapy for Neck Pain

Treatment Type	Percentage of Patients (%)
Allopathy	53%
Homeopathy	7%
Herbal Medicine	12.5%
Physiotherapy	14%
Massage Therapy	23%
Chiropractic Therapy	1.7%
Hot Pack Application	10%

Results about the hijama therapy history show that 75% of the study participant has experience of hijama therapy for other complaints and 64% of them had hijama therapy for neck pain. Only 23% had no history of hijama therapy.

Figure 1. Comparison of Neck Disability Index Scores Before and After Hijama Therapy

The average score of neck pain by NDI (neck disability index) in study group was 18.4 that is moderate before cupping therapy and decrease to 10 (mild) after cupping therapy. The decrease of pain scores between pre and post therapy was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) shown in Figure 1.

The VAS (visual analog scale) for neck pain pre hijama therapy was a mean of 5.5 that is moderate degree of pain which decreases to 2 which is less than mild after hijama therapy that is again statistically significant, shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Comparison of visual analog scale Before and After Hijama Therapy

Discussion

Among the various alternative methods, Wet cupping (Hijama) is long known to be beneficial in managing pains of different origins (Kouser, et al., 2021; Khan, et al., 2023; Javeria, Obaid, & Naseem, 2021). This is the first national intervention study investigating the effectiveness of Hijama therapy on neck pain.

Current study data showed that majority of the patients (98%), who visited Hijama clinics were female. This is in line with the global as well as local estimates that females are most likely to be affected by neck pain (Wu, et al., 2024; Kazeminasab, et al., 2022; Mughal, et al., 2024; Ahmed, et al., 2023). While neck pain typically affects middle-aged individuals, half the study participants were under 40, corroborating recent evidence by Mughal et al., Ahmed et al., and Ghafoor et al., Shows its growing prevalence among youth due to digital lifestyle habits (Kazeminasab, et al., 2022; Mughal, et al., 2024; Ahmed, et al., 2023; Ghafoor, et al., 2024).

The present findings indicate that a single Hijama session results in substantial reductions in neck pain and related functional disability confirmed by VAS and NDI tools by Saltychev et al and Delgado et al, has effectively captured clinical improvement in this study (Saltychev, et al., 2024; Delgado, et al., 2018). In the current study there is 65% reduction in VAS and 46% reduction in NDI scores post-Hijama exceed the minimal clinically important difference thresholds, indicating real-world benefits.

The immediate effects of dynamic cupping on mechanical neck pain, as reported by Jani et al, revealed rapid relief that persisted for several hours post-treatment, consistent with our findings (Jani, & Tank, 2020). The systemic review and meta-analysis of randomized clinical trials conducted in China, Japan and Korea concluded the cupping therapy to be effective for the neck pain along with significant improvement in the function and quality of life as well via mechanisms include improved

microcirculation, reduced oxidative stress, modulation of nociceptive pathways by release of endogenous opioids and endorphins (Saeed, et al., 2023; Niazi, Khan, & Jamil, 2023; Kouser, et al., 2021; Khan, et al., 2023; Javeria, Obaid, & Naseem, 2021). In this study, despite the invasive nature of wet cupping, most patients reported a sense of relaxation post-procedure. This subjective experience aligns with proposed mechanisms. However, four participants experienced transient fainting episodes during the procedure—a side effect which was previously reported in the literature (Rehman, Qureshi, & Iqbal, 2021).

Unlike many existing investigations focused on dry cupping (Wang, et al., 2023; Tehseen, et al., 2022), our study uniquely examines the outcomes of wet cupping. Further comparative evidence comes from a study by Ye et al., (2020) which evaluated acupuncture against two wet cupping techniques, both showing significant efficacy. Similarly, a clinical trial by Toausif et al. in India found Hijama to be more effective than Transcutaneous Electrical Nerve Stimulation (TENS) in reducing both pain and disability scores (Tausif, M. R., Ali, H., & Lari, A. R. (2017). In the present study, many participants had tried various other therapies before seeking Hijama treatment, and a considerable number had previously undergone Hijama as well. This prior experience reflects their trust in the therapy, a finding that is also documented in the literature (Mushtaq, & Nini, 2025, Saeed, et al., 2023).

Conclusion

This study contributes preliminary national data affirming Hijama's role as an adjunctive non-pharmacological treatment for neck pain. Given its cost-effectiveness and minimal side-effect profile, Hijama warrants integration into broader pain management strategies, especially in resource-constrained settings. This research outcomes also stresses upon the need to conduct rigorous awareness sessions for health lifestyles to avoid the health associated burden of neck pain.

Limitation

This study lacks control group. A short follow-up duration, and potential placebo effect can be noted in this study.

Conflict of Interest

None declared.

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